

INVESTIGATING LUNAR SURFACE TEMPERATURE: COMPARING A REGOLITH BOUNDARY LAYER THERMAL MODEL TO AN ANALYTIC FUNCTION. Alex Cui¹, Parvathy Prem¹, ¹Johns Hopkins University Applied Physics Laboratory, Laurel, MD

Background: Measurements of lunar surface temperature, combined with thermal modeling, can reveal key insights into surface composition and texture [1,2]. (Temperature is important in understanding volatile transport) [3]. We modeled the surface temperature of the Moon using two models, and compared the results. One model [3] reproduces measured brightness temperature data, which is emitted from a certain depth in the regolith, and thus is not true surface temperature. Due to the low conductivity of the lunar regolith, there may be significant temperature differences within this depth [4]. We aim to investigate the relationship between brightness temperature and temperature at varying depths within the emitting layer, referred to as the lunar epiregolith [5].

Methods: Thermal Model: The first model used was the Regolith Boundary Layer thermal model (“ReBL”), which solves the one-dimensional heat equation, using a Monte Carlo approach to compute the radiative flux term [6]. A finite differencing scheme is applied to solve for temperature, T as a function of depth, z and time, t for a specified latitude. The radiative flux incident at the surface varies with insolation over the course of the lunar day, and a constant heat flux of 0.018 W/m^2 from the lunar interior is assumed at depth. The key variables in this model are density, specific heat capacity, thermal conductivity (from [1]), as well as extinction coefficient, single scattering albedo, and asymmetry parameter at visible and infrared wavelengths, which control the scattering and absorption of solar and thermal radiation within the modeled regolith. The latter terms are computed assuming Mie scattering by $36 \mu\text{m}$ diameter spherical grains with the optical constants of enstatite [7,8] and a volume filling factor of 0.5.

Analytical Model: The second model was an analytic expression from [3]. This model reproduces measurements of brightness temperature from the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter Diviner instrument to a high degree of accuracy for dayside solar zenith angles of $< 80^\circ$ and night side solar zenith angles $> 100^\circ$. The expression does not take into account topographical features, compositional effects, or depth, and is least accurate near the terminator [3].

Results and Discussion: Figure 1 compares temperatures at 60, 250, 500, and 1000 μm (approximate) computed using ReBL to the brightness temperature. One interesting observation is the temperature at 60 μm calculated by the ReBL is the farthest from the brightness temperature. The temperatures increased up to 200

μm in depth, then decreased at a slower rate up to 1000 μm , as seen in Figure 2. The analytical model agrees with the thermal model most at daytime depths of 500-750 μm . Meanwhile, the night side temperatures consistently differ by around 100 K.

Figure 1. Temperature at varying depths within 1 mm (thermal model) and brightness temperature (analytic function)

Figure 2. Temperature as a function of depth on the lunar equator at noon

We will continue to investigate the two models by changing parameters, such as latitude, addressing the reasons for the differences between them.

References: [1] Hayne et al. (2017), *JGR*, 122, 2371-2400. [2] Lucey et al. (2021), *JGR*, 126, e2020JE006777. [3] Hurley et al. (2015), *Icarus*, 255, 159-163. [4] Henderson and Jakosky (1994), *JGR*, 99, 19063-19073. [5] Mendell and Noble (2010), *LPSC*, 1348. [6] Prem et. al (2022), *PSJ*, 3, 180. [7] Zeidler et al. (2015), *APJ*, 798, 125. [8] Huffman and Stapp (1971), *NPS*, 229, 45-46